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CONTENTS

WAYS TO EXPAND THE COMPANY'S POSITION IN THE FURNITURE MARKET	6
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM OF MEDICINAL PLANT PROCESSING	11
Usmonov Mirgulom Khoshim o'g'li	
POLITICAL RELATIONS BETWEEN AZERBAIJAN AND UZBEKISTAN: HISTORY, CHALLENGES, AND PROSPECTS	17
Naila Ramazanova	
ANALYZING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF REGIONAL ECONOMIES USING MULTI-CRITERIA INDICES AND MODEL OPTIMIZATION	23
Sattorov Sanjar Abdumurodovich	
ECONOMIC ADVANTAGES OF MODERNIZING THE EDUCATION SYSTEM THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES	28
Rakhmatkhodjayev Akhrorhodja Akmal ugli	
XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV VA INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISH MODELLARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI	34
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
DIGITALIZATION OF FOREIGN EXCHANGE DIFFERENCE ACCOUNTING: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS IN EMERGING ECONOMIES	41
Pulatov Sirojbek, Misirov Kamoldin	
ВЛИЯНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ДЕМОГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ НА ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ СТРАНЫ	47
Ташмухамедова Яйра Атхамовна	
MAIN MEASURES TO STRENGTHEN EMPLOYMENT STABILITY AND IMPROVE EMPLOYMENT MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	52
Abdullayeva Nigora Shamsiddinovna	
ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF INVESTMENTS ON THE CREATION OF NEW JOBS	57
Shayzak R. Kholmuminov, Shukhrat Sh. Kholmuminov	
RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA YASHIL TURIZM KONSEPSIYASI ASOSIDA TURIZM SOHASINING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHI	68
Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li	
IQTISODIYOTDA DAVLAT ISHTIROKINI QISQARTIRISH ORQALI XUSUSIY SEKTOR ROLINI OSHIRISHNING IJTIMOY MUHITGA TA'SIRI	73
Musurmonqulov Muhammad	
DIAGNOSIS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE DEVELOPMENT IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN: METHODS AND RESULTS	77
Abduxamidova Dilorom Abdumuminovna	
MULTIMADANIY MUHITDA PEDAGOGLARNING TANQIDIY FIKRLASH KO'NIKALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	81
Gulyamova Nafisa Burikulovna	
WAYS TO IMPROVE MARKETING SERVICES IN A FURNITURE MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISE	85
Mukhtarov Samadjon Abdusattor ugli	
THE ROLE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES (SMES) IN ENHANCING UZBEKISTAN'S EXPORT PERFORMANCE	90
Abduvoitov Bekzod Khikmatullaevich, Dr. Navik Istikomah, S.E., M.Si	
OPPORTUNITIES FOR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR WITH THE HELP OF AN INNOVATIVE IT PLATFORM	99
Nasrullaev Hikmatullo Habibulloevich	

DIGITALIZATION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS FOR EXPORT	105
Azimov R.B.	
IQTISODIYOTDA TO'G'RIDAN-TO'G'RI XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI ROLINI OSHIRISH	109
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna, Ro'ziqulov Abduqahhor Ixtiyor o'g'li	
SUSTAINABLE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION STRATEGIES FOR INTERNATIONAL TRADE	114
Kurolov Maksud Obitovich	
THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE METAL MARKET AND THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESSES IN IT	129
Musinov Dilshod Sultanovich	
ANALYSIS OF EXISTING TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEM OF WATERING GAS WELLS	134
Abdirazakov Akmal Ibrahimovich, Boymurodov Boynazar Muradillayevich	
РЕФОРМЫ РЕЛИГИОЗНО-ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СФЕРЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	140
Тиллябаева Гульсунхон Бахрамовна	
MODELS FOR ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES.....	144
Melibayeva Gulxon Nazrullayevna	
TEXTILES AND SEWING-KNITTING INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND PRODUCTION VOLUME FORECAST	152
Ikromova Takhmina Latifovna	

TEXTILES AND SEWING-KNITTING INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND PRODUCTION VOLUME FORECAST

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Abstract: This article examines the ways in which textile enterprises of the Samarkand region can increase their position in the republican and international markets, for which the analysis of marketing activities at enterprises and the application of new methods, approaches and mechanisms are used, and the analysis of yarn products as part of import operations of textile and knitted and garment products is considered.

Key words: enterprise, international market, mechanism, knitted and garment products, import, operation, analysis.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Samarqand viloyatidagi to'qimachilik korxonalarining respublika va xalqaro bozorlarda o'z mavqeini oshirish yo'llari ko'rib chiqiladi. Buning uchun korxonalarda marketing faoliyatini tahlil qilish, yangi usullar, yondashuvlar va mexanizmlarni qo'llash, shuningdek, to'qimachilik, trikotaj va tikuvchilik mahsulotlari import operatsiyalari tarkibida ip-kalava mahsulotlarini o'rganish nazarda tutiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: korxonona, xalqaro bozor, mexanizm, trikotaj va tikuvchilik mahsulotlari, import, ekspluatatsiya, tahlil.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются пути укрепления позиций текстильных предприятий Самаркандской области на республиканском и международном рынках, для чего используется анализ маркетинговой деятельности предприятий и применение новых методов, подходов и механизмов, а также анализ прядильной продукции в рамках импортных операций по текстильным и трикотажным и швейным изделиям.

Ключевые слова: Предприятие, международный рынок, механизм, трикотажные и швейные изделия, импорт, операция, анализ.

INTRODUCTION

The textile, garment, and knitwear industry is one of the fastest-growing industries in the world. The global textile and clothing market was valued at \$1,695.23 billion in 2024, and it is projected to grow at a CAGR of 7.7% through 2030.

The experience of countries with a developed textile industry shows that under favorable conditions created by the state, the development of this sector can become a turning point for the economic growth of the country and its regions. The policies pursued in China and India are clear examples of this.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a result of comprehensive measures aimed at developing the textile, garment, and knitwear industry and supporting the investment and export activities of enterprises in this sector, the production volume in 2024 amounted to 123.21 trillion soums, while the annual export potential of the sector reached \$2.9 billion.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Research in the field of marketing conducted in Uzbekistan over the years has been based on national characteristics, and it is necessary to recognize the scientists who have made significant contributions to the development of marketing theory. These include I. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, A. Sh. Bekmurodov, A. A. Fattakhov, M. R. Boltaboev, S. J. Ergashkhodjaeva, M. Kosimova, M. I. Ikramov, S. A. Musaeva, G. Sh. Khankeldieva, M. M. Akbarov, S. A. Abdullaeva, and others.

The research and scientific results obtained by these scholars have created the theoretical and methodological foundations of marketing activities in the textile industry. However, the globalization of the textile and clothing market, the emergence of new large players, and the formation of new methods of competition

are creating new challenges and risks for Uzbekistan's textile sector. Therefore, improving the methodology of marketing activities to ensure competitiveness in domestic and foreign markets has become an urgent issue.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research process employed a systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and selective observation methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To analyze the role of the textile and garment industry in the Samarkand region, it is necessary first to consider statistical data. Textile and clothing production represent one of the most important areas of regional industry.

Today, regional statistical data make it possible to analyze this sector in two main directions: textile production and clothing production (Table 1).

Table 1. Dynamics of textile and clothing production in Samarkand region in 2017-2024¹

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Manufacturing industry	8870.5	12941.7	15130.6	17396.2	21744.8	27963.5	31739.9	44786.7
Textile production	1764.7	2156.5	2166.9	3637.6	4390.0	5132.8	5809.7	7646.8
Clothing production	224.9	341.7	271.3	597.1	657.6	697.1	815.8	1206.8
Total textile and clothing production	1989.60	2498.20	2438.20	4234.70	5047.60	5829.90	6625.50	8853.60

As can be seen from the data in this table, the textile, garment, and knitwear industry of the region has developed rapidly during 2017–2024. In 2017, a total of 8,870.5 billion soums worth of products were produced, and by 2024 this figure reached 44,786.7 billion soums, which means it increased fivefold.

The object of our study — textile and clothing production — amounted to 1,989.6 billion soums in 2017 and increased to 8,853.6 billion soums in 2024, representing a 4.45-fold growth. From this, it can be concluded that other branches of the manufacturing industry have been developing at a faster pace than the textile and clothing sector.

At the same time, this sector remains one of the key components of the manufacturing industry (Table 2).

Table 2. The share of textile and clothing production in the manufacturing industry in the region in 2017-2024 (in%)

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Manufacturing industry	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Textile production	19.9	16.7	14.3	20.9	20.2	18.4	18.3	17.1
Clothing production	2.5	2.6	1.8	3.4	3.0	2.5	2.6	2.7
Total textile and clothing production	22.4	19.3	16.1	24.3	23.2	20.9	20.9	19.8

One fifth of the manufacturing industry consists of textiles and clothing, which means that this sector constitutes a significant part of the industrial structure. In recent years, however, a slight decrease in the share of the textile industry has been observed. In 2017, textile and clothing manufacturing accounted for 22.4% of the total manufacturing industry, whereas by 2024 this figure had decreased to 19.8%.

The share of textile production declined modestly during the observed period — from 19.9% in 2017 to 17.1% in 2024. Conversely, the share of clothing production increased from 2.5% in 2017 to 2.7% in 2024. The overall growth of production can also be seen in the diagram below.

When analyzing the dynamics of textile and clothing production in the Samarkand region, a stable upward trend is evident over the period 2010–2024. Based on this pattern, a production forecast for 2025–2030 can be developed using the exponential smoothing method.

¹ Compiled based on data from the Samarkand Regional Department of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Exponential Smoothing is a time series forecasting technique in which recent observations (the most recent years of the period) are given greater importance than older ones. The formula for simple exponential smoothing is as follows:

$$St = \alpha * Yt + (1 - \alpha) * St-1$$

Where: Yt is the actual number of rows;

St – the corrected number in the t-th period of the series;

α – correction coefficient ($0 < \alpha < 1$). If α approaches zero, the forecast takes into account more previous data, on the contrary, if it approaches one, the forecast considers the latest data to be extremely important. Taking into account the deep reforms in our country in recent years, we took the α -coefficient equal to 0.8. To carry out the forecast, we used data on production volumes by types of economic activity in the Samarkand region for 2010-2024².

Another method of forecasting economic series is Holt's Linear Trend Method, which combines the exponential correction of time series with the addition of a trend. This method combines two actions, namely, adjusting the current values of the series and adjusting the direction and magnitude of the series' change. The general forecast formula is then:

$$\hat{Y}_{t+h} = Lt + h * Tt$$

Where: Lt is the grade of the level;

Tt - trend estimate;

h is the forecast period.

The forecast made according to the Holt method is considered somewhat more accurate, since it takes into account the reforms taking place in our country. If we perform the calculations using the above data, we obtain the following results (Table 3).

Table 3. Forecast of textile and clothing production volumes in Samarkand region using exponential correction and Holt method, billion soums

Years	Exponential correction method	Holt method
2025	9722,818	9715,989
2026	11175,339	11167,629
2027	12627,860	12619,269
2028	14080,382	14070,909
2029	15532,903	15522,549
2030	16985,424	16974,189

The closeness of the forecasts in the table indicates that the calculations performed correspond to the current trends and trend lines. Based on this, it can be assumed with a high probability that the volume of textile and garment and knitwear production in Samarkand region in 2030 will reach 16,980 billion soums.

In the production of textile and clothing products, along with general economic indicators, indicators in physical volumes are of great economic and social importance (tons, sq. m., pieces, pairs, etc.). To continue the analysis of textile and clothing production, we tracked the physical changes in product production in the manufacturing industry (Table 4).

Table 4. Change in the physical volume index of industrial production in Samarkand region in 2017-2024, in percent³

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Manufacturing industry	124.3	112.4	106.0	105.4	112.5	109.3	106.5	108.4
Textile production	120.4	95.4	95.9	135.6	96.7	92.6	110.0	103.9
Clothing production	120.9	152.3	85.5	80.1	101.0	94.6	106.1	110.9

From the data in this table, it can be seen that the physical volume of total industrial production in the region has been steadily growing in 2017-2024. The average annual growth rate was at least 105.4 percent (in 2020), and the largest increase was 124.3 percent (in 2017). As for textile products, we can see a decrease in

2 Open data of the Samarkand regional department of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan (https://samstat.uz/uz/?preview=1&option=com_dropfiles&format=&task=frontfile_download&catid=286&id=5805&Itemid=100000000000)

3 Compiled based on data from the Samarkand Regional Department of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

physical volume in most years of the observed period. The physical volumes of clothing production have also changed unevenly, that is, while a significant increase was observed in 2017 and 2018, there was a decrease in 2019, 2020 and 2022 compared to the previous year. Starting from 2023, the volume of production has changed in line with the growth trend. An analysis of the physical volumes of product production shows a large number of unused reserves at the enterprises of the region.

The place of the textile and garment industry in the economy of the region can be assessed by its role in foreign economic activity. The production of textile and garment products constitutes the main part of the export potential of the region. A total of 14 types of textile and garment products are included in the foreign economic activity of the region (Table 5).

Table 5. Export indicators of textile and garment and knitwear products in Samarkand region

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Silk	875	6,962.60	10,556.10	12,026.80	13,609.30	17,513.40	15,661.70	11,319.40
Wool and wool yarn	269.9	0	0	0	0	46.8	0	0
Cotton	9 345.00	3,504.10	14,884.80	28 270.90	63,854.60	63,085.20	30 277.10	33,545.80
Other vegetable textile fibers	0	0	0	0	70.8	41.4	178.5	51.9
Chemical yarns	1 561.30	496.6	1 282.60	1 334.00	3,775.60	1,510.60	1 349.80	2 153.50
Chemical fiber	3,435.10	2 475.20	4 771.90	4 401.10	9 105.30	10,532.90	5 861.90	10 125.10
Other non-woven products	234.9	586.3	323.5	213.1	229.5	405	151.4	561.5
Total yarn	15721.2	14024.8	31818.9	46245.9	90645.1	93135.3	53480.4	57757.2
Carpets and other floor coverings	32422.90	29014.00	29811.10	27532.20	32223.60	23763.00	21185.20	21010.50
Total carpets	32422.9	29014.0	29811.1	27532.2	32223.6	23763.0	21185.2	21010.5
Special fabrics and trims	74.9	0	23.96	218	1,007.20	1,083.80	272.3	568
Textile products for technical purposes	0	0	98.9	178.8	262.1	12.7	28.8	87.3
Knitted fabrics	7.25	0.13	35.37	2 157.80	10 103.40	8,813.10	6 156.40	3,960.60
Total fabrics	82.15	0.13	158.23	2554.6	11372.7	9909.6	6457.5	4615.9
Knitted clothing products	10938.70	16589.8	20414.6	17187.00	24982.20	31097.20	37816.30	23077.4
Clothing products (except knitwear)	3829.50	4 684,00	4148.0	3,424.50	6,539.10	10,066.50	7,932.60	6149.20
Total clothing items	14768.2	21273.8	24562.6	20611.5	31521.3	41163.7	45748.9	29226.6
Other finished textile products	372.3	260.6	1,522.50	2,544.40	5,542.10	6 678.50	7 671.60	8832.5
Total	63366.75	64573.33	87873.33	99488.6	171304.8	174650.1	134543.6	121442.7

From the data in this table, it can be seen that the export indicators of textile and garment and knitwear products are not stable during the observed period. In particular, we can see that the situation with exports deteriorated in 2023-2024. The diagram below clearly demonstrates this situation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Changes in exports of textile and garment and knitwear products in Samarkand region in 2017-2024, billion soums

To analyze the export of textiles and clothing, we combined these fourteen product types included in the foreign economic commodity nomenclature into groups: yarn, carpets, fabrics, ready-made garments, and other finished textile products (Table 6).

Table 6. Structure of textile and knitwear exports in Samarkand region in 2017-2024, in percent

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Total yarn	25	22	36	46	53	53	40	48
Total carpets	51	45	34	28	19	14	16	17
Total fabrics	0	0	0	3	7	6	5	4
Total ready-made clothing products	23	33	28	21	18	24	34	24
Other finished textile products	1	0	2	3	3	4	6	7
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

From this table, we can see that during the observed period, the share of yarn and thread products in the export of textile and knitwear products increased (from 25% in 2017 to 48% in 2024), that is, we do not consider the shift of exports towards raw materials to be a positive situation. Of particular note is the sharp decrease in the share of carpet exports. At the same time, an increase in the export of fabrics and other finished textile products is observed.

If we divide products into finished (carpets, ready-made clothing, other types of finished textile products) and semi-finished (yarn, fabrics), in 2017 finished textile and sewing and knitting products accounted for 75% of the total sector's exports. By 2024, this figure had decreased to 48%. The share of semi-finished products, that is, products that serve as raw materials for the next stage of processing, in 2017 was 25% and by 2024 reached 52%.

We analyzed the share of textile and sewing and knitwear products in the import operations of the Samarkand region (Table 7).

Table 7. Import indicators of textile and sewing and knitted products in Samarkand region

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Yarn	28714.1	44946.2	44630.5	36727.2	44783.1	54454.4	68376.8	72483.3
Carpets	1.5	4.6	1.2	6.6	71.1	439	875.3	515.7
Fabrics	4,645.0	5,832.5	6,869.6	6891.8	9 226.1	12,095.2	16,332.4	13,053.3
Ready-made clothing products	433.5	1423.7	419.8	51.1	59.8	219.5	353.6	323.2
Other finished textile products	251.9	112.3	174.2	132.8	164	430.8	246.8	260.3
Total	34046.0	52319.3	52095.3	43809.5	54304.1	67638.9	86184.9	86635.8

In the structure of import operations of textile and knitwear and clothing products in Samarkand region, yarn and thread products occupy the main place (84.3% in 2017 and 83.6% in 2024). In second place is the import of fabrics, which accounted for 13.6% and 15.1% of imports, respectively. It can be concluded that the textile and knitwear and clothing industry of Samarkand region has a positive foreign economic balance, that is, the share of finished products in imports is very low (Table 8).

Table 8. Structure of imports of textile and knitwear products in Samarkand region in 2017-2024, in percent

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Yarn	84.3	85.8	85.6	83.3	82.5	80.5	79.3	83.6
Carpets	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.6	1.0	0.6
Fabrics	13.6	11.1	13.2	15.6	17.0	17.9	18.9	15.1
Clothing products	1.3	2.7	0.8	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.4
Other finished textile products	0.7	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.6	0.3	0.3
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

To estimate the level of net exports, we add up the obtained figures. We compared this with the volume of textile and clothing exports. From this diagram, it can be seen that the excess of textile and clothing exports over imports exceeded 66% in 2020, and by 2024 it had decreased to 34.7%.

We attribute this to increased activity in traditional markets and the discovery of new ones during the coronavirus pandemic. We believe that the decline in net exports in recent years is due to increased competition in the global and domestic textile markets and the opening up of the Uzbek economy. In order to provide a complete analysis of the export of the textile and garment and knitwear industry in the region, we determine the ratio of net exports to the volume of exports of products (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Ratio of net exports of textile and clothing products in Samarkand region to the total export volume of the region, in percent

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, based on the data in this diagram, in recent years, a downward trend has been observed in the change in net exports of textile products of the region. This indicator was 33.49 percent in 2023, and 26.26 percent in 2024. It can be concluded that the textile enterprises of the region need to increase their position in the republican and international markets. For this, it is advisable to analyze marketing activities at enterprises and apply best practices in applying new methods, approaches and mechanisms in it.

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